

Network Data Challenges 2021: wrap-up and recommendations

Introduction

Network needs for the HL-LHC are estimated in the [planning document](#). The estimates are divided in two models:

- minimal hierarchical - traffic going from T0 to T1, and then from T1 to local T2;
- flexible - more chaotic, with transfers ongoing also across Tiers i.e. T1-T1 and T2-T2.

Although the minimal model contains the two core use cases, the flexible one corresponds better to how experiments, particularly ATLAS and CMS, are already performing. It is foreseen to have a large-scale challenge every two years, between 2021 and 2027, with increased bandwidth. The 2027 challenge aims at covering the full HL-LHC requirement.

The 2021 Data Challenge (DC) is the first of these challenges and has two goals:

- generate enough traffic to reach and exceed the 480 Gb/s threshold of the minimal model;
- commission https as a third party protocol (TPC) in place of gsiftp at pledged sites.

The DC is designed with the following concepts as pillars.

- Use the production infrastructure of the experiments. This has the benefit of testing the presence of bottlenecks across production services, deeply focusing on the network.
- Inject data in a backfilling mode, with the production traffic contributing the most. The results are hence the sum of the production traffic and the DC-activity injected data.
- Use only disk endpoints for the injected data.
- Centralise the injection for all the participating experiments.
- Build a common dashboard to monitor the DC.

1 Infrastructure

The [wlcg-doma GitLab](#) group hosts several repositories, including [Data Challenge 2021](#). This is used as the main service to set up the central/common infrastructure. The documentation should be found at [DOMATPC-15](#).

A [k8s cluster](#) is deployed on the dedicated “WLCG DOMA” CERN OpenStack project, having a 4 vCPUs / 7.3 GB RAM master and a 16 vCPUs / 29.3 GB RAM node. Dedicated k8s-Pods are deployed in the node per experiment participating in the challenge, to ensure the proper environment is loaded along with [Rucio configurations and scripts](#).

The certificate

```
"/DC=ch/DC=cern/OU=Organic
Units/OU=Users/CN=rucio01/CN=663551/CN=Robot:      Rucio      Service
Account 01/CN=1319909346"
```

is used for both ATLAS and CMS, as both Rucio instances are instructed to recognise it as linked to account “rucio01” and “wlcg_data_challenge”, respectively, and a proxy is regularly [generated and propagated](#) to the related Pods.

1.1 Reasons to Centralise: Pros and Cons

A centralised infrastructure is proposed for the DC exercise for several reasons:

- coordinate the challenge across multiple experiments in terms of design, procedures, and injection;
- standardise the execution of the challenge;
- even out differences in knowledge in view of future Challenges;
- decouple experiment-related parts from the exercise to allow experiment-agnostic runners/experts (here WLCG-DC core team) to efficiently act on behalf of the experiments, avoiding duplication of similar tasks and waste of personpower/FTE.

The whole injection procedure is designed to run regardless of the experiment to act upon. However, a few considerations undermine the utility of such design, as detailed in the following.

The non-participation of 2 out of 4 experiments already reduces the benefit of such centralisation. In addition, the final design of the infrastructure depends specifically on the deployment and implementation of Rucio in the 2 participating experiments, used as the official Data Orchestrator. A further bottleneck is identified in the different setups used by the two experiments. As an example, the CMS Rucio account used for the DC has not enough privileges, and any action on transfer-rules is delegated to dedicated CMS teams (e.g. Transfer Team), creating delays as multiple person-layers are needed during the process ([4 Effort](#)).

On the other hand, centralising the operations is pivotal in the standardisation of tests and for on-the-fly changes. As the raw-unit of data volume (i.e. rucio containers) are standardised in terms of both creation and management, and the logging/bookkeeping of rule IDs is properly handled, tests can be adjusted, corrected, added and/or removed at will, even at short notice. The advantage of such a proposal is evident by analysing the variety of tests ATLAS is able to switch among during the DC week ([2.1.2 Tests](#)).

In view of future Network Data Challenges, and considering their ever-increasing targets, a similar sort of automation is more than advised.

2 Description of Tests and Objectives

The DC concerns the WLCG global traffic and is designed to produce traffic at a rate corresponding to the thresholds detailed in the [planning document](#), assessing the ability of T1s to cope with the resultant ingress and egress movements. The focus is not on saturating any particular network link.

The goal is to demonstrate the feasibility of network traffic of at least 480 Gbps (240 ingress + 240 egress). An estimated 2.592 PB volume should be moved in any 24h time period to achieve such targets.

As the normal production traffic already reaches - not continuously - the above thresholds, 240 Gbps is proposed for the 'Data Challenge' activity to double the target. ALICE and LHCb experiments do not contribute to this particular activity, hence their traffic refers to normal production activities. For this reason, the DC traffic should be shared between ATLAS and CMS as, potentially, 60-40, i.e. 1.555 PB ATLAS - 1.037 PB CMS. The shares have been chosen using the FTS traffic percentages over a period of 90 days during the month of May 2021.

2.1 ATLAS

ATLAS chooses to use the production Rucio Storage Elements (RSEs) during the DC. The maximum quota ATLAS can provide for the related RSEs is never reached with the exception of a few T2s, whose details are provided in the 'Result' section. Nevertheless, limits on the usage of storage for the DC are set per RSE, including a 200 TB free buffer that would prevent any disruption of production activities at those storage endpoints.

Reliable sites with large network bandwidth and storage, referred to as 'Nuclei', are selected for the tests: CERN-PROD_DATADISK T0, 12 T1s, and 24 T2s. The calculation of the volume of data for each individual transfer test, logically grouped in a Rucio container, is driven by the choice of volume decided to be moved in a 24h time period.

Therefore, containers of around 5 TB (Day 1-2) and 10 TB (Day 3-4) are used for all tests, and containers of around 90 TB are used for additional and dedicated T0-T1 tests (from Day 2).

2.1.1 Containers and selection of data

As real data are used, and Rucio does not move files already present at destination sites, a careful selection of data should be performed. A dedicated container is used per source site: 1 at T0, and 1 per T1. The datasets attached to each container exist only in 1 copy at the related source site, modulo their presence on TAPE storages or any other site which does not participate in the challenge. The files contained in each dataset have a probability of less than 0.1% being in any other relevant site.

A dedicated read-only account is set to access the ATLAS Rucio database (ADCR) for the selection of data. For completeness, the following query is performed:

```
SELECT cr.scope, cr.name, atlas_rucio.id2rse(cr.rse_id), cr.bytes, cr.length
FROM
atlas_rucio.collection_replicas cr,
(
```

```

SELECT scope, name, count(*) AS nr_dataset_replicas
FROM atlas_rucio.collection_replicas
WHERE state='A'
AND did_type='D'
AND scope NOT LIKE 'user%' AND scope NOT LIKE 'group%'
AND available_replicas_cnt = length
AND available_bytes BETWEEN $MIN AND $MAX
AND length<$LENGTH
GROUP BY scope, name
HAVING count(*)=1
) tmp
WHERE cr.scope=tmp.scope
AND cr.name=tmp.name
AND cr.state = 'A'
AND cr.available_replicas_cnt = length
AND atlas_rucio.id2rse(cr.rse_id)='$SITE'
ORDER BY atlas_rucio.id2rse(cr.rse_id) ASC;

```

where \$LENGTH is minimised, \$MAX-\$MIN < 1 TB, and \$SITE is either T0 or T1s.

The preferred option is to attach only 1 dataset per container. Consequently, each dataset has the same size as the related container, hence 5 TB and 10 TB. Nevertheless, 10 datasets are attached to each 90 TB container.

Containers are created in pairs, as similar as possible, to be interchangeable during the test of each link every other day. This allows Rucio to purge the transferred data at the end of the 24h period, ensuring they are not used in any of the subsequent tests.

2.1.2 Tests

Details concerning tests and calculation of the following numbers should be found at [WLCG DOMA Network Data Challenge 2021 spreadsheet](#). Please be aware that several sheets exist per experiment and per Day of Challenge within the same document.

- The DC_1 set of containers is used for Day 1, having attached only 1 dataset each of around 5 TB.
 Tests are as follows: 12 tests from T0 to T1s; 23 tests from T0 to T2s; 66 tests from T1 to T1s (*); 276 tests from T1 to T2s.
 (* In an A,B,C -Tier scenario, A→B, A→C, and B→C links are tested, but not B→A, C→A, and C→B)

Files to be moved: 402 861.
 Volume to be moved: 1.868(678) PB.
- The DC_2 set of containers, having attached only 1 dataset each of around 5 TB, and DC_SP2 container, having attached 10 datasets totalling around 90 TB, are used for Day 2.
 Tests are as follows: 12 tests from T0 to T1s; 12 additional dedicated tests from T0 to T1s; 24 tests from T0 to T2s (**); 132 tests from T1 to T1s; 288 tests from T1 to T2s (**).
 (** Addition of AGLT2_DATADISK)

Files to be moved: 724 246.
 Volume to be moved: 3.339(465) PB.
- The DC_S1 set of containers, having attached only 1 dataset each of around 10 TB, and DC_SP1 container, having attached 10 datasets totalling around 90 TB, are used for Day 3.
 Tests are as follows: 12 tests from T0 to T1s; 12 additional dedicated tests from T0 to T1s; 24 tests from T0 to T2s; 132 tests from T1 to T1s; 288 tests from T1 to T2s.

Files to be moved: 1.625(401) M.
 Volume to be moved: 5.620(390) PB.
- The DC_S2 set of containers, having attached only 1 dataset each of around 10 TB, and DC_SP2 container are used for Day 4.

Tests are as follows: 12 tests from T0 to T1s; 12 additional dedicated tests from T0 to T1s; 24 tests from T0 to T2s; 132 tests from T1 to T1s; 288 tests from T1 to T2s.

Files to be moved: 1.234(223) M.
Volume to be moved: 5.609(358) PB.

- The DC_SP1 container is used for Day 5.
Tests are as follows: 12 additional dedicated tests from T0 to T1s.

Files to be moved: 368 196.
Volume to be moved: 1.081(188) PB.

The lifetime of these transfers is set to expire at 0000 on October 11th (i.e. exceeding 24h). The lifetime of Thursday's DC_SP2 transfers is also set to expire at 0000 on October 11th.

2.2 CMS

The CMS '_Test' infrastructure is chosen to be used for the DC so as to clean up the space easily and safely after the challenge is complete, and also to simplify the data selection. The _Test RSEs share the same network link with the production RSEs; therefore, these are deemed suitable for the test. The RSEs use the same storage endpoints as the production ones, borrowing space from them. It should be noted that the Rucio storage usage was not properly set and reported in this '_Test' infrastructure.

Storage at CMS T2 sites is generally nearly full, and it is difficult to determine the space available for the challenge. The maximum quota CMS can provide for these RSEs are as follows: 25 TB at T0 (T2_CH_CERN_Test), 100 TB per each of the 7 T1s (T1*_Disk_Test), and 20 TB per each of the 26 T2s (T2*_Test). CMS chooses to test 26 T2 sites which have storage greater than 2PB, and are also commissioned with the WebDav protocol.

The calculation of the volume of each individual transfer test is mainly driven by two considerations:

- as the '_Test' infrastructure mostly contains no data, initial data placement is required, whose volume should be taken into account in the quotas reported above per Tier;
- the remaining available quota should be maximised in terms of the maximum size of the container to be received by a destination Tier, along with the other parallel tests using the same Tier as destination.

Therefore, containers of around 10 TB are used for tests involving T1s as destination and containers of around 2.5 TB are used for tests involving T2s.

Note that the small quota of 25 TB at disposal at T0 prevents the performance of additional and dedicated T0-T1 tests. However, these tests are performed by CMS during the tape challenge in the following week (reference to Tape Challenge post-mortem for further details).

2.2.1 Containers and selection of data

CMS decides to create 10TB (2.5TB) test containers using datasets with sizes around 1TB (1.25TB) and a minimum number of files to reduce the load on FTS.

The containers are transferred for the initial placement at the _Test instances, and a few containers have transfer issues: transfers are timing-out and failing due to large file sizes above 15 GB. Typical file size is between 5 to 7 GB.

There is a delay for CMS initial placement because some Heavylon datasets stored at T3_CH_CERN_OpenData are used. At a later stage, it emerges that these data can not be moved from the 'OpenSource' site due to settings in Rucio constraining them.

Containers are created in pairs, as similar as possible, to be interchangeable during the test of each link every other day. This allows Rucio to purge the transferred data at the end of the 24h period, ensuring they are not used in any of the subsequent tests.

2.2.2 Tests

Details concerning tests and calculation of the following numbers should be found at [WLCG DOMA Network Data Challenge 2021 spreadsheet](#). Please be aware that several sheets exist per experiment and per Day of Challenge within the same document.

Tests are as follows: 7 tests from T0 to T1s; 26 tests from T0 to T2s; 42 tests from T1 to T1s; 182 tests from T1 to T2s.

- The DC_1_10 (tests not involving T2s) and DC_1_2d5 (tests involving T2s) sets of containers, having attached datasets totalling around 10 and 2.5 TB, respectively, are used for Day 3.

Files to be moved: 171 750.

Volume to be moved: 1.008(447) PB.

- The DC_2_10 (tests not involving T2s) and DC_2_2d5 (tests involving T2s) sets of containers, having attached datasets totalling around 10 and 2.5 TB, respectively, are used for Day 4.

Files to be moved: 175 029.

Volume to be moved: 1.010(436) PB.

- The DC_1_10 and DC_1_2d5 sets of containers are used for Day 5.

Files to be moved: 171 750.

Volume to be moved: 1.008(447) PB.

The lifetime of these transfers is set to expire at 0000 on October 11th (i.e. exceeding 24h).

The volume moved by CMS is significantly lower than that transferred by ATLAS each day. CMS has considerably less disk space than ATLAS, and therefore is not able to provide the same resources for the DC.

3 Monitoring

This section covers the monitoring details that are associated with the DC. Part of this content can also be found in the dedicated markdown [documentation](#).

3.1 Infrastructure

In order to monitor and analyse the DC traffic, the existing [MONIT](#) infrastructure is employed. More specifically, the MONIT [Grafana instance](#) is used to create and view the visualizations along with some Elasticsearch data sources that represent data from the traffic.

3.1.1 Data Sources

Three main Elasticsearch data sources are used for the purpose of this challenge, all of them providing data that are enriched with WLCG-CRIC provided topology information.

- The main one is the *FTS Aggregated* data source which represents aggregations of FTS transfers (relevant [schema](#) in Kibana). This data source consists of FTS transfers that are aggregated into hourly bins. As an example, at 15:00+ the hourly bin 14:00 - 15:00 becomes available. Due to this aggregation, this data source is not meant for real-time monitoring but works more as a source to understand traffic trends over hours. This source holds data for all LHC experiments that make use of FTS, and the retention policy is unlimited. Most visualizations panels are based on this data source.
- A secondary data source is the *FTS Raw* data source which represents individual FTS transfers and state changes that these transfers follow. This data source is a better fit for real-time monitoring and it lays the foundations for the aggregations that are described in the previous source. It is used in two panels, and the retention policy is one month (although in the context of the DC, the relevant produced data are kept for more time, for the purpose of building new panels in the future).
- The third and final data source is the *WLCG Aggregated* data source which contains data from the *FTS Aggregated* data source and the *XRootD Aggregated* data source. This source is used to present a general view of the WLCG traffic (thus, XRootD traffic is also included) in contrast to the traffic that was induced by the DC.

3.1.2 Dashboard

The DC Grafana dashboard can be found under the WLCG organization ([Data Challenges / FTS Status Board](#)). This dashboard serves as the central monitoring portal for the aforementioned participating experiments. It consists of multiple panels with varying functionalities. The core ones concern:

- single value metrics (success rate of transfers, average throughput, volume transferred, etc.);
- general plots displaying trends of metrics of interest;
- pie charts displaying transfers breakdown to certain fields of interest;
- error and failure plots, pie charts, and links to the failed transfers log files;
- tape traffic specific metrics and plots;
- custom throughput tables for pairs of source/destination sites;
- efficiency/volume/throughput matrices for ATLAS, CMS, and LHCb.

Additionally, panels are implemented to give an insight on the network impact of the DC activity to WLCG in general, and specifically to participating Tier1s. These involve:

- WLCG FTS & XRootD throughput plot displaying the DC activity, along with the experiments' activities which are not connected to the DC;
- T1 plots and tables for incoming and outgoing throughput;
- breakdown of T1 throughput plots for each individual participating T1.

For all the aforementioned panels, there are extensive filtering capabilities to limit or expand the views, both from drop-down menus as well as from ad-hoc filtering on the data sources.

3.2 Evaluation

The evaluation of the monitoring capabilities relies on feedback from users that interact with the dashboard. During the implementation, there is an iterative process of evaluating the usability of the panels with respect to user needs, adjusting them accordingly. Certain topics, highlighted during this evaluation, are as follows.

- The central monitoring capabilities prove invaluable in displaying together multiple-experiment views. Tracking the progress of the challenge in multiple panels for multiple experiments provides a better overall view of the traffic. However, the DC dashboard also allows limiting the views to a single experiment.
- The error and failure plots/metrics help to identify occurring issues during the challenge. In combination with the grouping and filtering capabilities, this section of the dashboard is instrumental in pinpointing problematic sites and tackling the reasons for failed transfers.
- Even though the external site networking monitoring (LHCOPN, single VO) is challenging to integrate, the comparison of the DC dashboard visualizations with the equivalent site visualizations is a sufficient match, and contributes to the validation of the views.

3.2.1 Problematics & Caveats

Problems with data sources are figured out in the scope of providing a set of good monitoring tools not only to keep track of the DC activity, but also for any other activity involving FTS or XRootD transfers.

Various problems identified during the current exercise are listed as follows.

- Throughput calculation for FTS data. For the time being, a real throughput is impossible to be provided, as based on completed transfers. Thus, either one of the following should be referred to.
 - Throughput per transfer (useful for looking at specific transfers).
 - Global approximation (using the amount of bytes transferred divided by the visualisation bin).
- Missing fields for some experiments ("UNKNOWN" label used by default).

- Missing Tiers for some CMS data (not relevant to the DC, but exposed during the process).
- Incomplete set of labels for LHCb FTS transfers.
- Incomplete XRootD Data.
 - Various required fields are missing, leading to numerous integration efforts needed and not-fully-functional dashboards.
 - Often unclear what data represent.
- Poor (to absent) documentation about existing data sources and their fields.

4 Effort

For the first Data Challenge, 9 people are part of the DC core team:

1 MonIT, 2 WLCG/ESCAPE, 3 ATLAS, and 3 CMS.

The expertise covers:

- coordination;
- central infrastructure and injection;
- common monitoring;
- central Data Management (for the 2021 DC, only ATLAS);
This includes support from experiments with respect to production site status.
- CMS-specific Data Management (selection of data).
As outlined in [1.1 Reasons to Centralise: Pros and Cons](#), this latter effort is required as not enough privileges are awarded to the CMS Rucio account to be used for a “Centralised Data Management”.

Further meetings with network and XRootD experts are carried out as part of the DC to understand if it is possible to integrate site network monitoring and XRootD monitoring. These discussions are not planned to provide solutions to be integrated within the DC time frame.

5 Results

This section covers the network DC results, divided into analysis of the throughput, error analysis, and HTTP-TPC commissioning.

5.1 Throughput

The goal of the DC is to achieve 10% of the minimal model scenario, i.e. a global throughput of 480 Gbps. The throughput is defined as the 4 experiments' production traffic plus the data injected by ATLAS and CMS during the DC. Different views of such throughput are provided:

global throughput and ability to inject enough data during the DC; T1 ingress/egress traffic; T0-T1 traffic.

5.1.1 Global Throughput

The normal production traffic already reaches - not continuously - the minimal model threshold ([2 Description of Tests and Objectives](#)). The injection of the DC traffic allows it to exceed such threshold consistently, reaching 10% of the flexible model target, corresponding to 960 Gbps, over the DC week.

[Figure 1](#) shows the WLCG (FTS+XRootD) throughput during the 30-day time window used to run the DC and its preparation (Mock DCs), as well as the Tape Challenge. From a [random reference plot](#) ([9.1 Reference Global Throughput](#) - Appendix-Figure 1), it is clear that sustained traffic above the 480 Gbps minimal threshold is reached with standard production traffic. Therefore, the goal is to achieve the 960 Gbps flexible model target.

The injection of data during the DC is sufficient to exceed the 480 Gbps minimal threshold considering the DC traffic only. As a matter of fact, a maximum throughput of 64.5 GBps is reached ([9.1 Reference Global Throughput](#) - Appendix-Figure 2). As a side note, the Tape Challenge keeps the traffic above the minimal threshold with a combination of activities.

[Figure 1](#) - Mock DC1 22/09/2021; Mock DC2 01/10/2021; Network Challenge (DC) 04-10/10/2021; Tape Challenge 11-19/10/2021.

5.1.2 T1s Ingress/Egress

The amount of traffic produced by the DC activity towards a T1 could play an important role while assessing the site capability at reaching its goal as set in the [planning document](#). Specifically, considering the average throughput over a week - the default time window for the DC is set to be from **2021-10-04 09:00:00** to **2021-10-11 00:00:00**, the achievement of the target of a particular T1 might not be due to lack of network connectivity, but biased by e.g. lack of traffic.

To avoid such a problem, the following approach is followed:

1. if site is not **green (NOT OK)**, hence the average throughput is not above threshold, then use SUM of ingress and egress;
2. if after 1. site is still **(NOT OK)**, then use dedicated time window (4-day minimum);
 - a. (plus) then use SUM of ingress and egress.

T1	Flexible Scenario 2027	Minimal Scenario 2027	10% Minimal Scenario (2021 Targets) ingress/egress	Average ingress/egress (hourly)	Maximum ingress/egress (hourly)
CA-TRIUMF	400	200	10/10	17/26	49/71
DE-KIT	1200	600	30/30	26/42	77/143
ES-PIC	400	200	10/10	9/11	18/17
FR-CCIN2P3	1140	570	30/30	34/41	70/80
IT-INFN-CNAF	1380	690	30/30	23/40	50/87
KR-KISTI-GSDC	100	50	0	0	0
NDGF	280	140	10/10	26/26	49/81
NL-T1 (NIKHEF)	-	-	10/10	10/12	38/53
NL-T1 (SARA)	360	180	10/10	12/16	51/79
RU-JINR-T1	400	200	10/10	10/12	26/31
RU-NRC-KI-T1	240	120	10/10	9/12	18/34
TW-ASGC	-	-	10/10	8/6	16/13
UK-T1-RAL	1220	610	30/30	15/24	41/43
US-FNAL-CMS	1600	800	40/40	19/16	49/64
US-T1-BNL	900	450	20/20	29/38	75/117

[Table 1](#) - T1s ingress/egress averages and maxima during the DC.

[Table 1](#) shows that after the aforementioned procedure/caveats, only 3 sites remain to be explained: TW-ASGC, UK-T1-RAL, US-FNAL-CMS.

In [9.2 T1s Ingress/Egress](#), Appendix-Table 2 and Appendix-Figure 1,2, and 3 provide references of the results shown.

It should be noted that the global sum of average ingress/egress across T1s exceeds the targets (240/240) before the aforementioned approach: 242/309 as detailed in [9.2 T1s Ingress/Egress](#) - Appendix-Table 1.

TW-ASGC is a small T1 without TAPE storage, and is the farthest of the T1s. The site is considered to be OK for its size and characteristics (for the time being).

UK-T1-RAL has a unique storage system named ECHO. The ECHO implementation of HTTP-TPC generally works, but has some glaring performance problems (particularly in ingress). The ECHO code is being reviewed to assess if layers of buffers of different sizes are the issue. A network upgrade is also being carried out, aimed not only at increasing the bandwidth but also simplifying the internal site network.

US-FNAL-CMS has the largest bandwidth requirements: 40/40 Gbps. There is not enough production traffic to fill the bandwidth, nor the DC traffic is enough to backfill it. Ultimately, the lack of disk space and the difficulty to free it are the root causes of the failure of filling the bandwidth. The usage of `_Test` RSE might have aggravated the situation and further tests are recommended.

5.1.3 T0-T1 Traffic

T0-T1 traffic can be looked at in two ways: as LHCOPN traffic and as FTS T0-T1 traffic. The latter corresponds mainly to the specific use case of T0 export of RAW data to T1s, which is a subset of LHCOPN total traffic. The reason is that T1-T1 transfers route mostly through CERN, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - LHCOPN.

Both T0-T1 and T1-T1 tests are performed during the DC. The peak of combined traffic over LHCOPN is around twice the average traffic during the DC, nevertheless at the level of other production peaks highlighted in the past. The T0 network does not result in a bottleneck during the DC, and is not particularly stressed. Figure 3 shows continuous rates from the Tape Challenge, even though less data are injected. The DC does not have a continuous stream of data transfers, but requires instead deletion of data after each injection as a consequence of disk space limits.

Figure 3 - Data Challenge and Tape Challenge during Week 40 and 41, respectively.

5.2 Error Analysis

The error rate during the DC results to be lower than during the previous 9 months. The errors are mostly due to a handful of sites not working correctly, and to an application in the development stage moved to production during the DC week, which alone generates 4.3% of the errors. The fix of such arrives after the DC. However, better coordination within the experiments on parallel activities is a recommendation to avoid spurious errors during the future Challenges. None of the dominant errors are due to the DC itself.

	Successful	Failed
DC 04-10/10	84.09%	15.91%
DC+prod 04-10/10	81.11%	18.89%
Prod errors 01/01-30/09	78.13%	21.87%

5.3 HTTP-TPC Commissioning

The production stage of HTTP-TPC at the majority of sites is one of the main priorities for the DOMA TPC WG. The DC is carried out using HTTP-TPC as the final step of the commissioning process. HTTP-TPC is used for 84% of the transfers to and from disk, and out of 30.9 PB transferred during the DC using FTS, 28.2 PB relies on HTTP-TPC.

95% of sites have been migrated to use HTTP-TPC as bulk transfer protocol and the commissioning for these can be considered a success. Among the remaining handful of sites that still have to migrate UK-RAL-T1 is of particular concern because it is a large T1. Experiments can dedicate the remaining time before before Run-3 to the usual configuration cleanup necessary after a migration.

Figure 4 - Disk throughput grouped by protocol. Traffic includes production and DC activity.

5.4 Site Network Data

The current monitoring does not include site network (and tape) monitoring data, both for the inbound and outbound traffic. The comparisons performed using internal site monitoring or LHCOPN, e.g. [5.1.3 T0-T1 Traffic](#), have a qualitative nature due to differences in the visualisation tools. Despite the provided insight, it is challenging to match the intervals and the binning, as well as to sum or discriminate different types of traffic (e.g. IPv6 vs IPv4), different network paths (e.g. LHCOPN vs. LHCONE vs. general purpose), and different destination grouping.

The enabling of the NOTED SDN algorithm between PIC and CERN represents one of the most interesting events during the DC. The NOTED algorithm, depending on the FTS load, can direct the traffic to different channels effectively adding bandwidth when needed. In the DC case, LHCONE bandwidth is added to LHCOPN once LHCOPN is saturated. However, there is not a consistent visualization of all the portions of traffic while comparing the FTS throughput plots in Grafana.

Figure 5 shows an increase in the bandwidth during the DC, from 6 Gbps reported by the LHCOPN monitoring to 10 Gbps reported by FTS. This allows FTS to exceed 10 Gbps, which is the maximum limit on LHCOPN for the PIC link, during the Tape Challenge.

Figure 5 also shows the limits of a comparison between the network monitoring and the FTS monitoring due to lack of LHCONE traffic. Moreover, even including the latter as a plot, it would not be possible to separate out the T2 traffic on the current plots.

These considerations point towards a requirement of at least an integrated monitoring for T1s for the future understanding of networking.

Figure 5 - Comparison between the PIC LHCOPN internal monitoring and the FTS Grafana monitoring during the Data and Tape Challenges when NOTED SDN is enabled.

6 Rucio and FTS Performances

Figure 6 - Fast submission of transfers from Rucio to FTS, with no effect on the Rucio servers.

The ATLAS instance of Rucio is scrutinised in detail for its performance during the DC. During several Mock challenges before the DC, several improvements in the Rucio

deployments are applied: e.g. bulk size configurations for database fetches; number of daemons for parallel processing; configuration synchronisation between Rucio and FTS. This is mainly to address the submission time windows, to keep them as short as possible to fill the links in parallel. Shortly before the DC, a transfer job handling patch is deployed, that, while unnecessary for the challenge itself, allows the central machinery to work more efficiently due to quicker handling of partially complete transfers. Because of this, the links are appropriately saturated, and any effect of cancelled transfers are then due to timeouts. No particular increase in errors is observed. The effect of the DC on the overall Rucio operation is seamless, with the Rucio servers in continuous flat operation. No changes are made to the system deployment or configuration for the succeeding Tape Challenge. Overall, the rate of files poses no problem to Rucio.

Shortly before DC21 the FTS database was upgraded to MySQL8. This allowed for on-line DB bulk operations, which historically has been a source of IO locks. The Web Monitoring was also migrated to a read-only replica for performance improvements. Throughout DC21 a maximum depth of transfer queues of 342k transfers was achieved.

Figure 7 - Concurrent staging batches during the DC.

FTS has in general been able to take on more work since the removal of the “Cartesian product query” that was identified after the July FTS ATLAS incident. The “Cartesian product query” and its faster replacement were responsible for selecting the next staging requests to be worked on. ATLAS easily reached the imposed FTS limit of 1.2K concurrent staging batches. Certain configuration changes were done by the FTS team to allow ATLAS to reach the limit with fuller batches than before the challenge. CMS has been happily working with a maximum of 4K concurrent staging batches. The FTS service believes there is no longer any reason for a limit, and is planning to increase and eventually remove the limit.

7 Recommendations

7.1 Further Tests

It is recommended to repeat the challenge at sites that fail to achieve the threshold, in particular UK-T1-RAL and US-FNAL-CMS. For the latter, the injection strategy and the amount of data to be injected need to be tailored to the size of the bandwidth.

7.2 Data Challenge Setup

The DC setup is designed to test not only the network but also the limits of the production infrastructure when facing increased traffic such as that injected during the DC.

The DC demonstrates that disk space is the most limiting factor. Even though including writing to and reading from disk at the same time is still manageable during the 2021 DC, the recommendation for future challenges is to separate testing of the network and of the infrastructure.

Several recommendations are proposed with respect to usage of real data and production infrastructure, and disk space issues, as follows.

- A load generator of MockData should be considered to ensure the uniqueness of data to transfer at any destination site.
- A cleanup campaign should be performed on multiple replicas present at different sites and/or moving the whole data volume (to transfer during the challenge) at T0 is advised.
- Writing to /dev/null should be taken into consideration while testing the network.

7.3 Monitoring

The DC21 exercise gathers a group of data experts contributing to a common dashboard solution which is considerably useful for all the experiments (included under the WLCG scope). A set of initial plots are integrated in order to follow the DC activity, representing an initial base to establish requirements needed for the correct monitoring of activities.

7.3.1 Future Steps

Dashboards

The DC21 dashboard provides numerous functionalities/panels useful for users. However, it might be felt as verbose, leading to the necessity of some fragmentation. Some of the recommendations on that front are listed below:

- migrate the “real-time” monitoring panels and build a new WLCG dashboard based on the raw data sources (e.g. FTS team already makes use of this data);
- migrate certain sections to new dashboards and interlink them, providing this way a dashboard-wiki for WLCG;

- generalise panels that are customised for DC21. The dashboard views should be useful and easy to analyse independently for all experiments.

Data Sources

Recommendations that concern the problems on data sources follow.

- Make sure no XRootD packets are lost:
 - current collections model is losing around 60% of packets;
 - work has started in collaboration with OSG to address this.
- Identify the minimum required set of labels (across all experiments) and ensure their presence where needed:
 - for regular operations view;
 - for accounting purposes.
- Curation of the data to identify and fix missing information.

7.3.2 Organizing Future Work

The participation of the following categories/roles is required to address the problems listed in 3.2.1:

- Data experts: data expertise - knowledge of which data is useful in the plots (usually tool users)
- Tool developers: tool expertise - knowledge of which data can be provided by the tool
- Monitoring managers: monitoring tools expertise - knowledge of how to better integrate/visualise the needed data

Once the roles are known, the second point to address is the minimum required set of data for the dashboards to be fully usable. This needs to be:

- Consistent across experiments (avoid specific bits used only by a given experiment)
- Consistent across tools (i.e: FTS and XRootD should provide the same minimum sets of information)

The way to build this set of labels seems to be from top to bottom:

- What to visualise (dashboard)
- Which filters to have on top (variables/labels)
- Where are the inconsistencies (check the current data sources and find what is exactly missing) (Data experts)
- Can these labels be provided (Tool developers)
- How to integrate all within the monitoring infrastructure (Monitoring managers)

7.3.3 Site Monitoring

Integrated network monitoring was one of the functionalities that will be most needed to better understand network traffic when the throughput requirements will be higher. While the harmonisation of the experiments' monitoring and of the FTS and XRootD traffic have the priority, it is worth also recommending to integrate the network monitoring at least for the T1s which belong to LHCOPN and LHCONE and already have some common infrastructure and

data sources for the monitoring. It is also recommended this be done with the WLCG Network Throughput WG and Network Packet Marking WG.

8 Conclusions

The DC was a useful exercise to test the whole infrastructure at double the global transfer rates that the experiments can achieve in production. It was a good opportunity to learn about potential infrastructure limits for future challenges at increased rates and to start a common monitoring that proved useful now and can be further developed.

9 Appendix

9.1 Global Throughput

[Appendix-Figure 1](#)

Appendix-Figure 2

9.2 T1s Ingress/Egress

T1	Flexible Scenario 2027	Minimal Scenario 2027	10% Minimal Scenario 2021 Targets ingress/egress	Average ingress/egress (hourly)	Maximum ingress/egress (hourly)	Reference
CA-TRIUMF	400	200	10/10	17/26	49/71	CA-TRIUMF
DE-KIT	1200	600	30/30	26/42	77/143	DE-KIT
ES-PIC	400	200	10/10	9/11	18/17	ES-PIC
FR-CCIN2P3	1140	570	30/30	34/41	70/80	FR-CCIN2P3
IT-INFN-CNAF	1380	690	30/30	20/31	57/87	IT-INFN-CNAF
KR-KISTI-GSDC	100	50	0	0	0	KR-KISTI-GSDC
NDGF	280	140	10/10	26/26	49/81	NDGF
NL-T1 (NIKHEF)	-	-	10/10	10/12	38/53	NL-T1 (NIKHEF)
NL-T1 (SARA)	360	180	10/10	12/16	51/79	NL-T1 (SARA)
RU-JINR-T1	400	200	10/10	8/9	32/31	RU-JINR-T1
RU-NRC-KI-T1	240	120	10/10	9/12	18/34	RU-NRC-KI-T1
TW-ASGC	-	-	10/10	8/6	16/13	TW-ASGC
UK-T1-RAL	1220	610	30/30	15/24	41/43	UK-T1-RAL
US-FNAL-CMS	1600	800	40/40	19/16	49/64	US-FNAL-CMS
US-T1-BNL	900	450	20/20	29/38	75/117	US-T1-BNL
Atlantic link	2500	1250	60/60			
Sum	9620	4810	240/240	242/309		

Appendix-Table 1

T1	Flexible Scenario 2027	Minimal Scenario 2027	10% Minimal Scenario 2021 Targets ingress/egress	Average ingress/egress (hourly)	Maximum ingress/egress (hourly)	Reference	Comments	Time Window Default: 2021-10-04 09:00:00 to 2021-10-11 00:00:00
CA-TRIUMF	400	200	10/10	17/26	49/71	CA-TRIUMF		
DE-KIT	1200	600	30/30	26/42	77/143	DE-KIT	Sum OK	
ES-PIC	400	200	10/10	9/11	18/17	ES-PIC	Sum OK	
FR-CCIN2P3	1140	570	30/30	34/41	70/80	FR-CCIN2P3		
IT-INFN-CNAF	1380	690	30/30	23/40	50/87	IT-INFN-CNAF	Sum OK	2021-10-05 10:00:00 to 2021-10-09 10:00:00
KR-KISTI-GSDC	100	50	0	0	0	KR-KISTI-GSDC	Alice T1	
NDGF	280	140	10/10	26/26	49/81	NDGF		
NL-T1 (NIKHEF)	-	-	10/10	10/12	38/53	NL-T1 (NIKHEF)		
NL-T1 (SARA)	360	180	10/10	12/16	51/79	NL-T1 (SARA)		
RU-JINR-T1	400	200	10/10	10/12	26/31	RU-JINR-T1		2021-10-05 10:00:00 to 2021-10-09 10:00:00
RU-NRC-KI-T1	240	120	10/10	9/12	18/34	RU-NRC-KI-T1	Sum OK	
TW-ASGC	-	-	10/10	8/6	16/13	TW-ASGC	NOT OK	
UK-T1-RAL	1220	610	30/30	15/24	41/43	UK-T1-RAL	NOT OK	
US-FNAL-CMS	1600	800	40/40	19/16	49/64	US-FNAL-CMS	NOT OK	
US-T1-BNL	900	450	20/20	29/38	75/117	US-T1-BNL		
Atlantic link	2500	1250	60/60					
Sum	9620	4810	240/240	Meaningless Calculation				

Appendix-Table 2

Appendix-Figure 1

[Appendix-Figure 2](#)

[Appendix-Figure 3](#)

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